

Table 2. Yields of IR9224-73-2-2-3 and IR8423-132-6-2-2 at Omon, Haugiang, Vietnam.

Line, variety	Yield (t/ha)				Av
	Wet season		Dry season		
	1981	1982	1982	1983	
IR9224-73-2-2-3	6.1	4.5	4.2	6.5	5.3
IR8423-132-6-2-2	6.7	3.9	3.5	5.5	4.9
Check ^a	5.7	3.3	4.2	4.7	4.5
LSD 50/0	0.51	0.57	ns	0.85	

^aCheck variety: wet season 1981, NN 6A; other seasons, NN 7A.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Ratooning ability of some summer rices on saline-calcareous soil

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We conducted a field trial in summer 1979 at RAU Research Farm to determine the ratooning ability of Pusa 2-2 1, CR44-35, Pusa 33, NC1626, CR126-42-2, IET1444, and C8585. Soil was a calcareous silt loam with medium fertility, pH 8.7, and Ec 1.20 mmho/cm at 25°C.

Seeds were sown 16 Mar and 2 seedlings/hill were transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing on 19 Apr. The main crop received 120-18-17 kg NPK/ha. C8585 was harvested 16 Jul, NC1626 19 Jul, and other varieties were harvested 1 wk earlier, leaving a 15-cm stubble from ground level. The ratoon crop was hand weeded 15 d after the main crop was harvested, and 20 kg N/ha was top-dressed. The field remained saturated with occasional flooding up to 10-cm

depth. The crop was irrigated twice in addition to frequent monsoon rains. At maturity, the ratoon crop of NC1626 (intermediate) and C8585 (semidwarf) was harvested. Yields of other varieties were not recorded because of their poor ratooning ability.

The C8585 ratoon yielded 32% of the main crop yield, and NC1626 24% of its main crop yield (see table). When yields of the main and ratoon crops were combined, however, NC1626 yielded better overall.

The ratoon crop was 25% shorter than the main crop. Panicle-bearing shoots/hill of the ratoon seemed to be positively correlated with the number of panicle-bearing shoots/hill for the main crop. The reduction in the number of ripened grains/panicle of ratoon was more pronounced (20-26%) than panicle length reduction (8-11%). The ratoon crop had lower grain weight (more with NC 1626) than the main crop. The ratoon crop matured 70 d earlier than the main crop.

Grain yield, yield attributes, and other plant characters of main and ratoon crops of 2 short-duration summer rices, Bihar, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/m ^{2a}	Grains/panicle (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Duration (d)
NC1626 Main crop	4.1	131	444 (10)	95	20.5	21.6	125
NC1626 Ratoon	1.0	102	222 (5)	76	18.2	20.5	54
C8585 Main crop	3.5	90	488 (11)	84	19.1	19.8	122
C8585 Ratoon	1.1	65	311 (7)	62	17.5	19.2	52

^aFigures in parentheses indicate number of panicles/hill.

season. It has yielded well in many provinces.

Like previously released IRRI lines NN3A (IR36), NN6A (IR2307-247-2-2-3), and NN7A (IR2070-199-3-6-6), both newly released lines are resistant to most rice pests on the Delta except blast. They can be grown on slightly acid sulfate and saline soils. □

In Bihar, farmers usually plant one crop of early rice on medium uplands in wet season to ensure timely planting of subsequent upland crops. Besides increasing rice yield with less expenditure, growing a ratoon crop still permits timely planting of upland crops. Irrigation availability is, however, a prerequisite for a ratoon crop in this area. □

Mashuri for cultivation in the Cuu Long Delta of Vietnam

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Much of the Cuu Long River Delta (Vietnamese part of the Mekong Delta) still is planted to late-maturing local varieties which yield from 1.5 to 4 t/ha. We compared Mashuri, introduced through the International Rice Testing Program in 1980, with popular local varieties Trang Chum (deepwater), Trang Lun (acid sulfate tolerant), Tieu Doil (salinity tolerant), and Nang Huong (good quality). In 3 yr of evaluation, Mashuri yielded well (Table 1). It had shorter duration than local varieties, produced more grains/panicle, and had lodging resistance, wide adaptability, and good quality.

Mashuri, Trang Chum, and Trang Lun react similarly to common rice pests of the Cuu Long Delta. They are susceptible to brown planthopper (BPH) and sheath blight (ShB) and tolerant of leaf blast